

The MeerKAT International Giga-Hertz T...? Extragalactic Exploration (MIGHTEE) survey

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Galaxy Formation and Evolution

How and when were the first galaxies formed?

How do Baryons trace and affect the Dark Matter distribution?

How do we go from gas to stars in galaxies?

How does accretion onto black holes affect the evolution of galaxies?

What is the environmental influence?

What is MIGHTEE?

How do we observe galaxies at radio wavelengths?

- **Continuum**
 - Synchrotron emission at $<5\text{GHz}$ ✓
 - Free-Free emission at $>10\text{GHz}$
- **Spectral Line**
 - Atomic gas (HI) ✓
 - Cold molecular gas (e.g. CO, CII)
 - Masers (OH) ✓
- **Polarisation**
 - Magnetic fields in galaxies ✓
 - Rotation measure synthesis for probing line of sight ✓

MIGHTEE - Observational Strategy

- 20 sq.deg.
 - L-band (900-1700 MHz)
 - $<1\mu\text{Jy}$ (Factor of ~ 4 deeper than JVLA-COSMOS)
 - Milky Way at $z\sim 1$, SMGs to the EoR
 - 90 $\mu\text{Jy}/\text{beam}$ per 25kHz channel
 - HI detections to $z\sim 0.5$
 - ~ 1000 hours
 - S-band (2.5-3.5GHz)
 - 1.5 μJy rms (matched to L-band for typical $\alpha=-0.7$ spectral index)
 - ~ 7 sq.deg (~ 650 hours) in subareas of COSMOS, CDFS, ES1
- LADUMA overlap – 1.5 sq.deg. In Continuum and Polarisation

20 sq.deg - why?

The cosmic history of star formation

Star forming galaxies dominate the source counts at $<100 \mu\text{Jy}$

Along with radio-quiet AGN (regardless of obscuration)
- See White, MJJ et al. 2015, 2017

The cosmic history of star formation

Dust Uncorrected

Dust Corrected

Madau & Dickinson 2014

SFR density uncertain due to dust

MIGHTEE will provide a dust-free probe of SF history to $z \sim 4$

Given good ancillary data can do this as a function of stellar mass, halo mass and proximity to AGN

AGN evolution and Feedback

Exponential cut-off at the bright end of the luminosity function

Fabian et al. 2006

AGN evolution and Feedback

Measuring the evolution of the AGN provides information on the kinetic feedback from radio jets

Smolcic et al. 2017
JVLA-COSMOS survey

The link to Dark Matter

Scenario 1

Scenario 2

Scenario 3

The evolution of activity in different DM haloes

Modelling of the cross-correlation function with a quenching term

HI absorption: The fuelling of AGN

- The complex interplay between AGN and gas is a vital component in the evolution of galaxies
- Radio-loud AGN form a dichotomy at other wavelengths, thought to be driven by mode of gas accretion:

High-Excitation RGs

- Strong emission lines
- Late-type hosts
- Cold-mode accretion
- Classical accretion disc

Low-Excitation RGs

- No emission lines
- Early-type hosts
- Hot-mode accretion
- Bondi-Hoyle or turbulent

- In both cases AGN injection of energy into the gas self-regulates the fuelling and couples the evolution of the host to the supermassive black hole

HI absorption: The fuelling of AGN

Maccagni et al. (2014, 2016)

- HI clouds kinematically decoupled from regularly rotating atomic gas
- Infalling from halo gas?

Frank et al. (2016)

NGC 3998

- Low-luminosity LERG
- Early-type galaxy

- Alignment of warping seen in the stellar and inner HI discs, and radio lobes
- HI clouds in inner disc could lose angular momentum and accrete onto AGN

Outflows and disturbed gas in compact radio sources

- High-sensitivity HI absorption (<1% opacity) can reveal evidence of **jet-driven** neutral gas at almost 1000 km/s ($\sim 10 M_{\odot}$ per year)
- Multi-wavelength follow up show concurrent **molecular** and **ionised** gas outflows
- Constrain models of early jet-ISM coupling (Wagner et al. 2012)

Morganti et al. (2013)

4C 12.50

MIGHTEE – HI and the evolution of HI

Maddox, Jarvis & Oosterloo, 2016

MIGHTEE – HI and the evolution of HI

MIGHTEE – HI: Resolved Galaxies

- Areal coverage of MIGHTEE gives reasonable cosmological volume at $z < 0.1$
- Kinematic analysis on 100's of resolved galaxies
- Rotations Curves and Mass Modelling for a statistically significant sample

How many star forming galaxies with polarisation?

- MeerKAT
500-1000 galaxies per sq deg
15,000 galaxies
- RM with 1 rad m^{-1} precision with average separation of a few arcminutes

Stil et al. 2009

Observational Strategy & updated time request

- ECDIFS – 03 30 -28 00 (LADUMA field + ~6sq.deg)
- XMM-LSS – 02 18 -05 00 (7.5 sq.deg)
- ES1 – 00 40 00 -44 00 00 (3 sq.deg)
- COSMOS – 10 00 +02 00 (1.5 sq.deg)

VISTA-VIDEO

3 degrees

1.5 degrees

VIDEO Survey in
XMMLSS
Jarvis et al. 2013

~1.2 Million galaxies

Multi-wavelength coverage of the MIGHTEE fields

LSST, DES, HSC,
CFHTLS, VST,
VOICE

UltraVISTA+VIDEO
VEILS
Euclid

HerMES/H-GOODS

SCOSMOS/S
ERVS/SpUDS
etc

CDFS/XMM-LS

Adding very low-frequencies...

LOFAR HBA XMM-LSS Field

380uJy rms in 4hours

16 more hours
scheduled will lead to
factor >2
improvement
(equivalent to ~30uJy
in L-band)

Feasible to use
international LOFAR
baselines to gain
~0.5arcsec resolution
(Morabito et al.in
prep)

MeerKAT is real

MeerKAT progress update

June 2016 – 16 antenna array completed

March 2017 – 32 antenna array completed

March 2018 – 64 antenna array completed

32 MeerKAT antennas in the Karoo. Different subsets of these were used to generate the images in this presentation. The square box (which is 1.2 kilometers on the side) shows a zoomed in version of the MeerKAT core.

MeerKAT-32 AR-1.5

Hydrogen in M33

Evolving observations of a distant radio galaxy

Summary

- ◆ MIGHTEE will be a key extragalactic survey covering many science aims
 - History of SF in the Universe,
 - The impact and fueling of AGN
 - The evolution of hydrogen
 - The evolution of magnetic fields
 - The impact of magnetic fields on galaxy and cluster evolution
 - Tracing the dark matter distribution from the cosmic web to clusters
- ◆ With data from other facilities we will be able to trace all processes that govern galaxy formation and evolution, from the cold neutral reservoir, to the molecular gas through to the SF and stellar mass already in place.
- ◆ Importantly we can do this over enough cosmic volume to understand the role of environment as a function of redshift

Summary

◆ Philosophy

- Strong SA leadership across all key science
- Open collaboration for people wanting to do work 😊
- Strong and open links with other MeerKAT projects
- Development of wide science aims towards formulating SKA KSPs

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Thanks!